

RECORDS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM UTILIZATION AND EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION IN OUR LADY OF FATIMA UNIVERSITY

Sharmaine Joy D. Fulgar, MBA

*Laguna College of Business and Arts School of Graduate Studies
City of Calamba, Laguna, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14042971>

ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study was to determine the relationship between records management system (RMS) utilization and employee satisfaction within Our Lady of Fatima University (OLFU). The research sought to pinpoint areas for improvement within the RMS, such as interface intuitiveness, data integrity, and security training, with the goal of enhancing user satisfaction and maximizing the benefits derived from the system's utilization. The study utilized a descriptive correlational design to examine the relationship between the utilization of records management systems and employee satisfaction within a university setting. Additionally, simple random sampling was utilized to select 100 respondents, comprising employees from various departments across selected campuses. The research instrument used in this study was a researcher-made survey questionnaire and the statistical treatment employed was four-point Likert Scale to describe the level of utilization and employee satisfaction of the RMS. Furthermore, the Pearson Product Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the relationship between RMS utilization and employee satisfaction in the University. The findings revealed a significant relationship between records management system utilization and employee's satisfaction in OLFU. There was a low positive to high positive relationship, while the computed probability values were lesser than the level of significant; thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. Moreover, areas such as interface intuitiveness, data integrity, and security training were identified as needing improvement to further enhance user satisfaction and the benefits derived from the utilization of the Records Management System.

Keywords: *Records Management System (RMS), Employee Satisfaction, Utilization, Interface Intuitiveness, Data Integrity, Security Training*

INTRODUCTION

Organizations implemented systems to make operations smooth, efficient, and secure, and one such critical system was the Records Management System (RMS). An RMS provided a centralized platform for managing records throughout their lifecycle, offering features for organizing, storing, retrieving, and securing both physical and digital records. By implementing an RMS, organizations could streamline record-keeping processes, improve access to information, ensure compliance with regulatory requirements, and mitigate risks associated with data breaches or legal disputes. This system enhanced productivity by reducing the time and effort required for manual record management tasks, allowing employees to focus on more strategic activities. Moreover, an RMS facilitated decision-making processes by providing accurate and up-to-date information, fostering operational smoothness and resilience within the organization.

Numerous organizations had challenges with defective records management systems, largely stemming from a lack of recognition for their crucial role in overall operations. Frequently, firms failed to recognize the need for effective records administration, considering it less important than primary business tasks. In essence, the lack of emphasis and financial commitment towards implementing strong records management systems could have a domino effect on a company's functioning, hindering efficiency and putting long-term success at risk. Adopting digital solutions instead of paper-based record-keeping could greatly save expenses related to physical storage. Utilizing digital storage was frequently more economical and enabled more efficient usage of workplace space, hence enhancing total cost-effectiveness.

In developed nations like the United States and the United Kingdom, the rapid pace of technological advancement had left numerous companies dealing with the consequences of fragmented and siloed records management systems, as mentioned by Pennix (2020). The intricate nature of these economies, with a multitude of industries and stringent regulatory bodies, amplified the challenges. Companies in these regions often faced difficulties in integrating various record-keeping systems across departments, hindering seamless collaboration and impeding agile decision-making processes. Additionally, the risk of cybersecurity threats and data breaches was heightened due to outdated systems that may have lacked robust security measures, according to Touray (2021).

Additionally, putting in place and keeping up with a good records management system had become a significant issue in many universities and colleges across the Philippines. It was challenging to keep records safe, organized, and easy to find in academic institutions because they were so complicated and contained a vast amount of management and academic data. Problems such as old or inefficient systems, uneven ways of entering data, and a lack of standard processes made it harder for an RMS to work at its best. Malak (2022) mentioned that, in the Philippines, implementing records management systems in schools and universities encountered challenges mainly due to resource constraints and technological limitations. This resulted in problems like insufficient storage facilities, obsolete software, and inadequate training for staff members

in charge of record management. The absence of standardized procedures and policies for record-keeping led to inconsistencies and inefficiencies in organizing, accessing, and maintaining information.

Furthermore, if there were problems with a university's records management system, it affected how happy users were with it. A lot of the time, employees needed to be able to quickly and accurately access different kinds of records, like academic papers, enrollment information, and financial records. If the RMS was not working right, it could have taken longer to get important papers, made it harder to get data, and made routine tasks less efficient overall. Users might have become frustrated, which could have made their experience with the university's administrative services worse and perhaps even changed how they saw the institution's general competence and efficiency.

Moreover, employees' contentment with the RMS had consequences for their performance, persistence, and overall working experience. An efficiently designed and user-friendly RMS improved employees' capacity to navigate administrative procedures easily, minimizing frustration and optimizing their work experience. However, dissatisfaction with the RMS could have resulted in heightened stress, reduced engagement, and potentially elevated attrition rates, as employees might have felt burdened by complex systems.

Therefore, the study's goal was to determine the extent to which universities utilized their records management systems by examining factors such as the integration of systems, data accuracy, and accessibility. By testing the effectiveness of these systems, this research aimed to identify any weaknesses or areas for improvement that might have hindered the smooth flow of information.

Research Questions

Generally, the study's primary goal was to examine the efficiency of records management system and employee satisfaction in selected campus of Our Lady of Fatima University. In the end, it sought to develop a strategy for enhancing the operational performance and satisfaction of user by utilizing the records management system.

Specifically, it was directed to answer the following questions:

Research Question 1. What is the records management system utilization level of OLFU as assessed by employees in terms of:

- 1.1. System Adoption and Integration,
- 1.2. User Accessibility and Interface, and
- 1.3. System Upgrades and Maintenance?

Research Question 2. What is the satisfaction level among the employees on the records management system utilization of OLFU in terms of:

- 2.1. Data Accuracy and Integrity,
- 2.2. Access and Retrieval Efficiency, and
- 2.3. Security Measures?

Research Question 3. Is there a significant relationship between the records management system utilization and the end-user satisfaction in OLFU?

Research Question 4. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

A thorough overview of the study's main components is found in this chapter. This chapter includes information on the research design that was used to carry out the study. Additionally, included are the research locale, population and sampling, respondents of the study, instrument, validation of instrument, data gathering procedure, and treatment of quantitative data.

Research Design

This study used a quantitative research approach with a utilization of researcher-made survey questionnaire instrument. Using this strategy, the researcher was able to observe and documented the subject offices' actual situations, problems, services, and programs. This strategy also provides a better understanding of the rationale behind these records management practices. The study did not demand complete involvement from the respondents, it did not create any delay or disturbance in the institution's everyday business activities.

Conversely, descriptive correlational design was used to identify connections between variables and facilitate the forecasting of future occurrences based on current understanding. Further discussion of correlational and descriptive research was provided by Ishtiaq (2019) & Creswell et al., (2014). In order to test theories or provide answers to inquiries about the participants' current employment status, descriptive research collected data that described and documented the state of affairs. In contrast, correlational research looked for and assessed the strength of a relationship between two or more quantitative variables.

Research Locale

Selected campuses of Our Lady of Fatima University (OLFU) with selected key offices or users of the RMS were participated on this study. Because of budget and time constraints, the researcher would not able to conduct face-to-face survey and campus visits. For some campuses that was not able to visit, the researcher requested from the other respondents to answer it via google forms.

Population and Sampling

The simple random sampling method was applied in selecting the respondents of this study to minimize selection bias and enhance the reliability and validity of the findings. This involves the employees from selected campuses in Our Lady of Fatima University. Moreover, the G*Power was utilized to determine the required sample size. The study aimed to include 100 respondents, specifying an effect size of 0.30 and a confidence level of 95%.

Respondents of the Study

This study was able to tap 100 respondents that came from selected campuses of Our Lady of Fatima University (OLFU). Employees from selected offices in OLFU—the registrar's office, the admissions office, the student financial services, and other departments who used the RMS—were asked to participate. These Offices could adequately represent the entire university for this particular study as these offices are the heart of major business activities of the university. The main respondents will ask to answer the questionnaire which captured the actual record management practices in OLFU.

Table A

Respondents of the Study

Group of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
OLFU Campus 1	40	40.00%
OLFU Campus 2	36	36.00%
OLFU Campus 3	24	24.00%
TOTAL	100	100.00%

Instrument

The primary research instruments of this study were a researcher-made survey questionnaire, and a review of literature and documentation. The researcher developed a questionnaire based on the cited literatures in this paper related to records management system and users' satisfaction. The questionnaire composed of two parts with corresponding questions for each part: Part I covered the level of utilization in records management system which contained the questions to capture the actual practices in each office and Part II assessed the level of satisfaction of employees in the records management system. The questionnaire gathered responses using 4-point Likert scales. For every response, a numerical score was assigned, which indicated the level of attitudinal favorability based on the following:

Arbitrary Scale for the Level of Utilization in Records Management System in Our Lady of Fatima University

Range	Rating	Level of Utilization on RMS	Verbal Interpretation
3.25-4.00	4	Always	Fully Utilized
2.50-3.24	2	Often	Utilized
1.75-2.49	2	Sometimes	Partially Utilized
1.00-1.74	1	Never	Not Utilized

Arbitrary Scale for the Level of Users' Satisfaction on Records Management System in Our Lady of Fatima University

Range	Rating	Level of Utilization in RMS	Verbal Interpretation
3.25-4.00	4	Strongly Agree	Fully Satisfied
2.50-3.24	2	Agree	Satisfied
1.75-2.49	2	Disagree	Partially Satisfied
1.00-1.74	1	Strongly Disagree	Not Satisfied

Validation of the Instrument

The researcher's questionnaire was presented to the thesis adviser for additional analysis and feedback. After developing and completing the questionnaire, it was validated by professionals in the field of study to ensure its technical accuracy and relevance to the topic. The validators included the appointed statistician, the school's research director, and a professor with prior experience validating research instruments. The questionnaire was revised based on specific suggestions and comments. Furthermore, the reliability and consistency of the questionnaire were assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding values of .930 for the independent variable and .938 for the dependent variable.

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher made a written communication to the university president and a letter of request to the designated offices. Following the President's approval, the researcher wrote to the campus administrator requesting for permission to conduct surveys and site visits. Upon the approval of the said request, a copy of the survey form was forwarded to the respondents' G Suite (Google Workspace) account or university email address. After the survey, the researcher-made questionnaire was collected, analyzed and interpreted. Followed by the consultation from the statistician for the interpretation of data.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical consideration was addressed in this study, which involved the participation of university employees. The survey research prioritized safeguarding the rights and well-being of participants and ensuring the integrity of data collection. This included obtaining informed consent from participants, maintaining anonymity and confidentiality throughout the survey process. Participants were assured that data security measures were in place to protect their privacy, and the survey design and implementation upheld principles of fairness and equity.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

The researcher used frequency and percentage to show the respondents' data. This research also determined the literary ability degree of employee satisfaction with records management efficiency using a weighted mean.

The following are the statistical treatments applied to the study by statistician:

1. The mean and the four-point Likert Scale were used to describe the level of utilization and level of user satisfaction on records management system in Our Lady of Fatima University.
2. To establish the relationship between the generational cohort and the manifestation of the work-related issues, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to measure that quantifies the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two continuous variables. It was used to determine the relationship of records management system utilization to user satisfaction in Our Lady of Fatima University.

Scope and Delimitation

By employing a descriptive-correlational design, this study aimed to establish the relationship between the records management system utilization level and satisfaction level of employees. This approach allowed a greater understanding on how specific elements of records management influence the employee satisfaction matrix. This study

assessed the comprehensive examination of the relationship of the two variables to have a basis for records management enhancement and service development. The researcher acknowledged that records management and archives management were inseparable. This study focuses primarily on active, semi-active, and inactive records, so records management was the study's main focus.

The level of records management system utilization encompassed system adoption and integration, user accessibility and interface, and system upgrades and maintenance. On the other hand, the employee satisfaction in Our Lady of Fatima University covered the data accuracy, integrity, access and retrieval efficiency, and security measures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter provides the interpretation and analysis of the data collected in order to address the solutions to the research problems of the study. The discussion follows the sequence how the statements of the problem are laid out in the first chapter.

Research Question 1. What is the records management system utilization level of Our Lady of Fatima University as assessed by employees in terms of:

1.1 System Adoption and Integration

Table 1.1

Records Management System Utilization Level of Our Lady of Fatima University as Assessed by the Employees in terms of System Adoption and Integration

Indicators in terms of System Adoption and Integration	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
I am familiar with the RMS implemented in our organization.	4.00	FU	1
I use RMS regularly for my work tasks	3.89	FU	5
The RMS seamlessly integrates into my daily workflow	3.77	FU	8
The RMS has improved collaboration and communication among different departments within our organization.	3.94	FU	3.5
Aligns well with the workflows and processes of our organization.	3.94	FU	3.5
The RMS has become an essential tool for performing my job efficiently.	3.84	FU	6
The system provides analytics or reporting features that help in monitoring and evaluating records management activities.	3.78	FU	7
The transition from our previous records management to the current one was smooth and efficient.	3.97	FU	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.89	FU	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Always/ Fully Utilized (FU) 1.75 – 2.49 Sometimes/ Partially Utilized (PU)

Our Lady of Fatima University Records Management System utilization level in terms of System Adoption and Integration was **Fully Utilized** (3.89) as assessed by the employees. Furthermore, the indicator “Employee is familiar with the RMS implemented in our organization” had the highest computed mean of 4.00 and was interpreted as Fully Utilized. Meanwhile, the indicator “The RMS seamlessly integrates into my daily workflow” had the lowest computed mean of 3.77 and was interpreted as Fully Utilized.

Moreover, this indicated that employees had received adequate training or had sufficient exposure to the system, leading to a solid understanding of its functions and features. However, despite their familiarity with the RMS, challenges were noted in how well the system integrated into their daily tasks. The findings still reflected a generally positive perception, but there was evident potential for enhancing the system's seamlessness within the workflow.

With the above result, Haddad et al, (2022) confirmed that the level of support from management was crucial for the adoption of the system. When leadership actively promoted and prioritized the use of the records management system, employees were more inclined to adopt it. This support often involved allocating resources for training, providing incentives for system utilization, and establishing clear expectations for its implementation. Ensuring compatibility with existing systems and technologies was also identified as pivotal for seamless integration. Challenges such as communication issues between the records management system and other tools, or complexities in data migration, were noted to potentially hinder adoption and diminish its effectiveness.

Moreover, Abebe (2019) noted that the adoption and integration of a records management system had a significant impact on its utilization within an organization. The seamless integration of a system into existing workflows and processes facilitated user adoption into their daily tasks. If the adoption process was complex or if the system was not well integrated with other tools and platforms, users might have been reluctant to use it, resulting in underutilization.

1.2 User Accessibility and Interface

Table 1.2

Records Management System Utilization Level of Our Lady of Fatima University as Assessed by the Employees in terms of User Accessibility and Interface

Indicators in terms of User Accessibility and Interface	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
The user interface of our RMS is intuitive and easy to navigate.	3.71	FU	8
I can easily locate the information I need within the records management system.	3.95	FU	1
The interface of the RMS is visually appealing and conducive to efficient work.	3.84	FU	6.5

The RMS offers customizable features to tailor the interface according to user preferences.	3.94	FU	2
The training provided for using the RMS adequately prepares users to navigate the interface.	3.91	FU	3
The RMS allows for easy collaboration and sharing of information among users.	3.88	FU	5
The system allows users to easily import and export data in various formats.	3.84	FU	6.5
The interface design is responsive and adapts well to different devices.	3.90	FU	4
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.87	FU	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Always/ Fully Utilized (FU) 1.75 – 2.49 Sometimes/ Partially Utilized (PU)
2.50 – 3.24 Often/ Utilized (A) 1.00 – 1.74 Never/ Not Utilized (NU)

Our Lady of Fatima University Records Management System utilization level in terms of User Accessibility and Interface was **Fully Utilized (3.87)** as assessed by the employees. Furthermore, the indicator “Employee can easily locate the information they need within the records management system” had the highest computed mean of 3.95 and was interpreted as Fully Utilized. Meanwhile, the indicator “The user interface of our RMS is intuitive and easy to navigate” had the lowest computed mean of 3.71 and was interpreted as Fully Utilized.

It implied that the system likely provided effective search functionalities or organizational structures that helped users quickly locate desired information. However, despite users being able to locate information relatively easily, there were concerns regarding the intuitiveness and navigability of the RMS user interface. Although it had a generally positive sentiment, there were still aspects of the interface that could have been improved to enhance user experience.

Pandey et al. (2021) discussed that a user-friendly interface that was easy to use could greatly improve user experience and promote adoption. Users were more likely to effectively utilize a system when they could easily navigate it, find necessary information, and complete tasks efficiently. Thus, a complicated or unwieldy interface could cause annoyance and opposition, leading to limited use of the system. Mukne et al. (2020) mentioned that creating a system that incorporated accessibility features like keyboard shortcuts, screen reader compatibility, and adjustable font sizes could enhance inclusivity and broaden its audience. The theory emphasized the importance of designing products and interfaces that were intuitive, easy to use, and aligned with users' needs and expectations.

1.3 System Upgrades and Maintenance

Table 1.3

Records Management System Utilization Level of Our Lady of Fatima University as Assessed by the Employee in terms of System Upgrades and Maintenance

Indicators in terms of System Upgrades and Maintenance	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
Regular upgrades and updates are performed to enhance its performance and security.	3.71	FU	3.5
The process of upgrading the RMS is seamless and does not disrupt our daily operations.	3.26	FU	9
The organization provides adequate training and support to users following system upgrades to ensure a smooth transition.	3.54	FU	8
The upgraded versions of the RMS offer new features and functionalities that improve user experience and efficiency.	3.68	FU	6
The system downtime during maintenance activities is minimal and does not significantly affect our productivity.	3.20	U	10
The RMS is flexible enough to accommodate changes in regulatory requirements or industry standards through updates or modifications.	3.61	FU	7
Users are provided with sufficient documentation or training materials to help them understand any changes or new features introduced through system upgrades.	3.75	FU	2
The organization has established protocols for data backup and disaster recovery to minimize the risk of data loss during system upgrades or maintenance.	3.79	FU	1
The records management system undergoes rigorous testing procedures before and after upgrades to ensure compatibility and stability.	3.71	FU	3.5
Our organization actively seeks feedback from users to identify areas for improvement in the records management system following upgrades or maintenance.	3.69	FU	5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.59	FU	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Always/ Fully Utilized (FU) 1.75 – 2.49 Sometimes/ Partially Utilized (PU)
2.50 – 3.24 Often/ Utilized (A) 1.00 – 1.74 Never/ Not Utilized (NU)

Our Lady of Fatima University Records Management System utilization level in terms of System Upgrades and Maintenance was **Fully Utilized** (3.59) as assessed by the employees. Furthermore, the indicator “The organization has established protocols for data backup and disaster recovery to minimize the risk of data loss during system upgrades or maintenance” had the highest computed mean of 3.79 and was interpreted as Fully Utilized. Meanwhile, the indicator “The system downtime during maintenance activities is minimal and does not significantly affect our productivity” had the lowest computed mean of 3.20 and was interpreted as Utilized.

Furthermore, this could have indicated that there was likely a structured approach to managing data integrity and minimizing the risk of data loss during system upgrades or maintenance activities. However, despite the presence of protocols for data backup and disaster recovery, there were concerns regarding the impact of system downtime on productivity during maintenance activities. It suggested that the user felt that system downtime did have a notable impact on productivity, although not excessively severe.

Jeon et al., (2019) emphasized the importance of creating redundant copies of critical data to protect against loss or corruption. In the context of system upgrades or maintenance, data backup protocols ensured that essential information was regularly backed up before any changes were made to the system. This practice enabled the organization to restore data to its pre-upgrade or pre-maintenance state in the event of an unexpected failure or data loss incident. The theory behind establishing protocols for data backup and disaster recovery during system upgrades or maintenance aligned with principles of risk management, disaster recovery planning, data backup, and continuity planning. By implementing these protocols, organizations could minimize the risk of data loss, protect business continuity, and ensure the integrity of critical information systems.

Moreover, the frequency and effectiveness of system upgrades and maintenance directly influenced the utilization of a records management system. Regular updates were essential to keep the system current with the latest security patches, bug fixes, and feature improvements. Insufficient maintenance could make the system susceptible to security risks, cause performance issues, or lead to incompatibility with other software and hardware, resulting in reduced efficiency. Engaging users in the upgrade process through feedback and addressing concerns enhanced their sense of ownership and engagement, thereby boosting their willingness to use the system.

Additionally, Ofori et al. (2022) discussed that clear communication regarding future upgrades and maintenance schedules was crucial to reducing user disruption and upholding trust in the system. Organizations were advised to give prior notice of scheduled downtime, explain the benefits of upgrades, and offer support services to assist users during the transition phase.

Furthermore, this reduced the likelihood of unforeseen problems occurring after the upgrade and decreased interruptions to business activities. Creating precise procedures for continuous system maintenance, including routine backups, performance monitoring, and troubleshooting protocols, helped prevent downtime and maintained peak system performance. Organizations could optimize the use of their records management system and ensure its long-term effectiveness by focusing on system upgrades and maintenance, as well as engaging users in the process.

Research Question 2. What is the satisfaction level of employees on the records management system in Our Lady of Fatima University in terms of:

2.1 Data Accuracy and Integrity

Table 2.1

Satisfaction Level of Employees on the Records Management System in Our Lady of Fatima University in terms of Data Accuracy and Integrity

Indicators in terms of Data Accuracy and Integrity	X	VI	Rank
The data accuracy in our RMS is crucial for the efficient functioning of our organization.	3.86	FS	3
The university provides sufficient support and resources for students to verify and rectify any inaccuracies in their records.	3.97	FS	1
The data within the RMS is consistently accurate and reliable.	3.68	FS	8
I rarely encounter discrepancies or inconsistencies in the data retrieved from the RMS.	3.30	FS	9
There are clear procedures in place for employees to report inaccuracies they encounter in the records.	3.83	FS	4
The university provides adequate training to ensure employees understand the importance of data accuracy in records management.	3.82	FS	5.5
Employees are encouraged to double-check data entries for accuracy before finalizing them.	3.82	FS	5.5
The university communicates effectively with students regarding any changes or updates to their records.	3.77	FS	7
The university's records management system effectively captures and maintains historical data relevant to my academic or administrative records.	3.87	FS	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.77	FS	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Fully Satisfied
2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Satisfied

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Partially Satisfied
1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Satisfied

The satisfaction level of employees on the Records Management System in Our Lady of Fatima University in terms of Data Accuracy and Integrity was Fully Satisfied (3.77). Furthermore, the indicator “The university provides sufficient support and resources for students to verify and rectify any inaccuracies in their records.” had the highest computed mean of 3.97 and was interpreted as fully satisfied. Meanwhile, the indicator “Employee rarely encounter discrepancies or inconsistencies in the data retrieved from the RMS.” had the lowest computed mean of 3.30 and was interpreted as Fully Satisfied.

Moreover, this suggested that there was a robust system in place to address concerns regarding data accuracy and integrity from the student's perspective. However,

despite the university providing support for students to rectify inaccuracies, it appeared that respondents still frequently encountered discrepancies or inconsistencies in the data retrieved from the records management system. This indicated significant concerns regarding the reliability and integrity of the data stored within the RMS.

With the given result, Edmans et al. (2019) discussed that efficient access and retrieval were crucial for employees' satisfaction with a records management system, especially in a school setting. Having user-friendly search functionality and well-organized navigation pathways significantly enhanced the user experience. The provision of adequate support and resources for students to verify and rectify any inaccuracies in their records was essential. This ensured the accuracy and integrity of the information stored in the system, fostering trust between the institution and its students.

Therefore, Guerrini et al. (2019) noted that accurate and reliable student records facilitated administrative staff in performing tasks such as enrollment management, academic advising, and graduation clearance more effectively. Conversely, inaccurate or incomplete data could result in administrative errors, delays in processing student requests, and inefficiencies in workflow. These issues not only frustrated students but also increased the workload and pressure on administrative staff, ultimately affecting overall satisfaction with the records management system.

2.2 Access and Retrieval Efficiency

Table 2.2

Satisfaction Level of Employees on the Records Management System in Our Lady of Fatima University in terms of Access and Retrieval Efficiency

Indicators in terms of Access and Retrieval Efficiency	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
The system I use for accessing information is user-friendly.	3.83	FS	5.5
I can easily find the information I need within the system.	3.83	FS	5.5
The search function in the system effectively retrieves relevant information.	3.90	FS	2.5
The system provides quick access to frequently accessed documents or resources.	3.90	FS	2.5
The organization and categorization of information within the system are clear and intuitive.	3.90	FS	2.5
The system offers multiple ways to retrieve information.	3.66	FS	8.5
The system helps me save time when searching for information.	3.90	FS	2.5
I rarely encounter errors or inaccuracies when retrieving information from the system.	3.32	FS	10
The system offers personalized recommendations or suggestions based on my previous searches or preferences, enhancing retrieval efficiency.	3.66	FS	8.5

I am satisfied with the overall efficiency of the system in accessing and retrieving information.	3.73	FS	7
---	------	----	---

GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.76	FS
---------------------------	-------------	-----------

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Fully Satisfied
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Satisfied
 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Partially Satisfied
 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Satisfied

The satisfaction level of employees on the Records Management System in Our Lady of Fatima University in terms of Access and Retrieval Efficiency was **Fully Satisfied** (3.76). Furthermore, the indicator “The search function in the system effectively retrieves relevant information; the system provides quick access to frequently accessed documents or resources; and the system helps me save time when searching for information.” had the highest computed mean of 3.90 and was interpreted as fully satisfied. Meanwhile, the indicator “Employees’ rarely encounter errors or inaccuracies when retrieving information from the system” had the lowest computed mean of 3.32 and was interpreted as Fully Satisfied.

Furthermore, this result implied that the system's search function was effective in retrieving relevant information and providing quick access to frequently accessed documents or resources. This suggested that the system positively contributed to users' efficiency by saving them time during information retrieval tasks. However, despite the perceived efficiency of the search function, it appeared that respondents frequently encountered errors or inaccuracies when retrieving information from the system. This indicated significant concerns regarding the reliability and accuracy of the information retrieved from the system.

According to Edmans et al. (2023), access and retrieval efficiency were critical factors that influenced employees' satisfaction with a records management system in a school setting. Efficient access to information allowed employees to quickly and easily retrieve the records they required, such as academic transcripts, course materials, or administrative forms. A well-designed records management system had easy-to-use search functionality and organized navigation pathways, enabling them to find information quickly. When students could access their records without delays or obstacles, they felt empowered and in control of their academic journey, contributing to higher levels of satisfaction.

Meanwhile, Lee et al. (2019) underscored the critical link between system reliability and user satisfaction in information systems research. By conceptualizing reliability, presenting empirical evidence, discussing theoretical frameworks, and outlining practical implications, the paper emphasized that reliable systems, characterized by consistent performance and accurate information delivery, led to higher levels of user satisfaction and trust. The authors advocated for strategies to improve system reliability, such as investing in infrastructure, implementing quality control measures, and providing user training. They also highlighted the need for further research to explore specific factors influencing user perceptions and the cultural contexts shaping the importance of

reliability. Overall, the paper highlighted the paramount importance of reliability in shaping user experiences and organizational success in information systems.

2.3 Security Measures

Table 2.3

Satisfaction Level of Employees on the Records Management System in Our Lady of Fatima University in terms of Security Measures

Indicators in terms of Security Measures	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
I am required to use strong and unique passwords to access the system.	3.91	FS	4.5
The system prompts me to update my password regularly to enhance security.	3.98	FS	1
The system automatically logs me out after a period of inactivity to prevent unauthorized access.	3.91	FS	4.5
The system restricts access to sensitive information based on user roles and permissions.	3.94	FS	2
Data backup and disaster recovery procedures are implemented to prevent data loss in case of emergencies.	3.82	FS	8
I am provided with security training or resources to help me understand best practices for protecting my account.	3.70	FS	9
The system has a clear and accessible privacy policy outlining how my data is collected, used, and protected.	3.87	FS	6
The system complies with relevant data protection regulations to ensure the privacy and security of user data.	3.85	FS	7
Regular security patches and updates are applied to the system to address known vulnerabilities.	3.92	FS	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.88	FS	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/ Fully Satisfied
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree/ Satisfied
 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree/ Partially Satisfied
 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree/ Not Satisfied

The satisfaction level of employees on the Records Management System in Our Lady of Fatima University in terms of Security Measures was **Fully Satisfied** (3.88). Furthermore, the indicator “The system prompts me to update my password regularly to enhance security” had the highest computed mean of 3.98 and was interpreted as fully satisfied. Meanwhile, the indicator “Employees’ provided with security training or resources that help them understand best practices for protecting their account” had the lowest computed mean of 3.70 and was interpreted as Fully Satisfied.

Moreover, the system effectively prompts them to update their passwords regularly. Regular password updates are a fundamental aspect of cybersecurity best practices, and the high mean score suggests that users appreciate this security measure

in place. However, despite the effectiveness of password update prompts, it appears that respondents feel less supported in terms of receiving security training or resources to understand best practices for protecting their accounts. It suggested that there may be room for improvement in educating users about account security measures.

To further explain, Guerrini et al. (2019) discussed that strong security protocols instilled trust and confidence in employees regarding the safety and privacy of their files. When employees were confident that their data was safe from unauthorized access or breaches, they were more likely to be satisfied with the overall management system. Implementing encryption techniques, access controls, and regular security audits helped improve the perception of safety and satisfaction.

Additionally, Aktar et al. (2021) mentioned that clear communication about security measures was critical for establishing trust and satisfaction. Schools that openly communicated their security policies and procedures showed a commitment to protecting records. Employees understood the value of their privacy when they were given clear explanations of how data was collected, stored, and used, as well as insights into the security measures in place. This transparency promoted a positive relationship between employees and the records management system, leading to increased satisfaction. Moreover, user-friendly security features increased employees' satisfaction with the records management system. Systems that prioritized usability while maintaining strong security measures were more likely to receive positive feedback from employees. Intuitive interfaces for accessing and updating records, combined with seamless authentication processes, improved the user experience. When security measures were seamlessly integrated into the system without interfering with usability, employees perceived the system as reliable and convenient, further enhancing their satisfaction.

Thus, Yeo et al. (2022) discussed that continuous improvement and adaptation of security measures to evolving threats and technological advancements were critical for maintaining employee satisfaction. As the cybersecurity landscape changed, schools needed to be vigilant and proactive in upgrading their security infrastructure. Regular assessments of security protocols, adoption of emerging technologies, and staff training on best practices all helped ensure that the records management system remained resilient to emerging threats. Schools could improve employees' long-term satisfaction with their records management system by anticipating potential risks and demonstrating a commitment to maintaining robust security measures.

Research Question 3. Is there a significant relationship between the records management system utilization and the employee satisfaction in Our Lady of Fatima University?

Table 3

Test of Significant Relationship between Records Management System Utilization and the User Satisfaction in Our Lady of Fatima University

Records Management System Utilization	Employee Satisfaction	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
System Adoption and Integration	Data Accuracy and Integrity	.386**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Access and Retrieval Efficiency	.535**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Security Measures	.582**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
User Accessibility and Interface	Data Accuracy and Integrity	.319**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Access and Retrieval Efficiency	.590**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Security Measures	.572**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
System Upgrades and Maintenance	Data Accuracy and Integrity	.834**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Access and Retrieval Efficiency	.556**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Security Measures	.679**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

There was a low positive to high positive relationship between records management system utilization and the employee's satisfaction (r-values .319 to .834) in Our Lady of Fatima University. The computed probability values .000 were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

The records management system utilization has significant relationship with employee satisfaction in Our Lady of Fatima University. The higher the records management system utilization, the higher the employees' satisfaction. If Our Lady of Fatima University fosters a culture that valued and promoted effective records management practices, users were more likely to perceive the RMS as valuable and reliable, leading to higher satisfaction levels. By recognizing and fostering the relationship between RMS utilization and user satisfaction, the university can enhance the

effectiveness of its records management practices and promote a positive user experience with the records management system.

The relationship between records management system utilization and employee satisfaction is an important but understudied area of educational technology. While it seems intuitive that an efficient RMS should improve employee satisfaction by providing easy access to academic records and administrative services, there are few solid and recent studies that focus solely on this topic.

Overall, the conclusion that Records Management System utilization was positively related to employee satisfaction in Our Lady of Fatima University was supported by theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence in the fields of information systems, records management, user-centric design, and organizational behavior. Clements et al. (2023) discussed that system usage was one of the key determinants of employee satisfaction. If users perceived that the records management system was useful, easy to use, and reliable, they were more likely to use it more frequently and derive greater satisfaction from its use.

Research Question 4. Based on the findings, what action plan may be proposed?

As a result of this study, it became evident that Our Lady of Fatima University could significantly benefit from implementing a comprehensive training and development program focused on improving the effectiveness and utilization level of its records management system. The findings highlighted specific areas for improvement, including interface intuitiveness, data integrity, and security training. Addressing these areas could further enhance employee satisfaction and optimize the benefits derived from the utilization of the records management system.

In addition, enhancing data integrity and security training is crucial to ensure that sensitive information remains protected and that users understand their role in maintaining data integrity. By educating employees on best practices for data handling, storage, and security protocols, the university can mitigate the risk of data breaches and unauthorized access, thus safeguarding the integrity and confidentiality of sensitive information.

Furthermore, implementing a targeted training and development program based on the findings of this study is essential for Our Lady of Fatima University to maximize user satisfaction and fully leverage the benefits of its records management system. By addressing areas such as interface intuitiveness, data integrity, and security training, the university can enhance employee satisfaction, improve operational efficiency, and ultimately achieve its organizational goals more effectively.

Table 4

Proposed Action Plan

General Objective: To enhance the training and development program of Records Management System utilization and to improve the User Satisfaction in Our Lady of Fatima University.

Key Areas	Objectives	Strategies/Activities	Persons Involved	Success Indicators
Interface Intuitiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To enhance clear and efficient navigation structure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design a clear and intuitive navigation structure. Use descriptive and consistent labels for navigation elements to aid user understanding. 	- For system provider	- 80-100% has resulted in a significant increase in the number of tasks completed per unit of time.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To incorporate feedback mechanisms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide immediate feedback to monitor user interactions and identify areas where feedback mechanisms can be improved. 	-For Employees: Users of the RMS.	- 80-100% has led to a major improvement in the RMS based on the number of reported issues resolved through user feedback.
Data Integrity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To enhance the data accuracy and to refine the precision and reliability of the data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure that the data stored in the RMS is correct and reflects the actual information accurately. Comparison of data across different records and databases within the RMS to identify and resolve inconsistencies. 	-For Employees: specifically, users that has editing tools access in the system.	- 80-100% has increased data entry error detection and correction during validation.
Security Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To understand the security risks and data protection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Educate employees on the potential risks associated with the Records Management System to ensure they grasp the importance of security measures. 	-For department heads and staff: users of the RMS	-80-100% has enhanced employees' understanding of data protection practices within the RMS environment.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To enhance the user accountability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Foster a culture of accountability by emphasizing the individual responsibility of each user in maintaining the security of the RMS. 	-For department heads and staff: users of the RMS	-80-100% has ensured that employees take proactive measures to protect sensitive information and uphold security standards.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions may be derived:

1. That the utilization of the records management system in the university demonstrated a commendable level of system adoption and integration, ensuring seamless user accessibility and interface. Overall, while the system was well-integrated and accessible to employees, continuous efforts towards maintenance and

upgrades were imperative to uphold its functionality and utility within the university ecosystem.

2. That the satisfaction levels of employees regarding the records management system in the university were notably high, as evidenced by the system's demonstrated accuracy and integrity of data, efficient access and retrieval processes, and robust security measures. This indicated a successful implementation and maintenance of the system, ensuring it met the needs and expectations of employees.

3. That the analysis of records management utilization at OLFU indicated a positive correlation between system usage and employee satisfaction, highlighting the importance of enhancing interface intuitiveness, data accuracy, system security, and minimizing downtime during maintenance.

4. The proposed action plan for OLFU emphasizing the importance of seamless integration of the records management system into daily workflows for maximizing employee satisfaction is needed. These necessitated continuous improvement efforts such as feedback collection, user training, and prompt issue resolution. Investing in RMS enhancements was regarded as a strategic priority for the university, as it directly impacted operational efficiency, user satisfaction, and overall organizational effectiveness.

Recommendations

This study aimed to explore how the records management system is being utilized at Our Lady of Fatima University and its impact on employee satisfaction. With the given findings, this study serves as a guide in providing insights for enhancing the system and improving employee training and services. To enhance the records management utilization and foster greater user satisfaction, several key recommendations are essential:

1. The university may prioritize improving the intuitiveness and user friendliness of the records management system interface through user experience research and redesign efforts. The university should prioritize improving the intuitiveness and user-friendliness of its records management system interface through user experience. A more intuitive system may enhance usability and efficiency, increasing productivity and user satisfaction. It may simplify training and onboarding, making it easier for new users to become proficient. An accessible design may ensure inclusivity for all users, including those with disabilities. Additionally, a user-friendly interface may help maintain data integrity and compliance with regulatory requirements. Prioritizing these efforts may foster continuous improvement, ensuring the system evolves with user needs and technological advancements, ultimately creating a more efficient and satisfying environment for all users.

2. Measuring the data accuracy and integrity, such as implementing robust data quality assurance processes and providing resources for users to report discrepancies may be considered. Minimizing system downtime during maintenance activities and enhancing security training and resources for users are vital steps to bolstering system reliability and user confidence. Additionally, promoting user engagement through feedback channels and continuously monitoring and improving records management system performance based on user needs and feedback are integral to sustaining high levels of employee satisfaction over time.
3. Given the significant relationship between records management system utilization and employee satisfaction at OLFU, it is imperative to capitalize on this finding to enhance organizational effectiveness. Implementing strategies to further streamline and optimize the records management system may not only improve administrative processes but also bolster employee satisfaction levels.
4. The proposed action plan for OLFU prioritized the seamless integration of the records management system into daily workflows to enhance employee satisfaction. This involved continuous improvement strategies like feedback collection, user training, and prompt issue resolution. Training and support were offered to staff to acquaint them with the redesigned interface and enhanced features of the records management system. By executing this action plan, OLFU sought to maximize the utilization of the records management system, boost user satisfaction, and elevate the overall user experience.
5. For future research, it is suggested to investigate the long-term effects of the implemented training and support on employee productivity and efficiency. Additionally, exploring the potential correlation between enhanced records management system utilization and academic performance metrics could provide valuable insights for educational institutions. Furthermore, examining the scalability and adaptability of the implemented action plan to other departments or institutions could offer valuable guidance for broader implementation strategies in similar academic settings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical consideration was addressed in this study, which involved the participation of university employees. The survey research prioritized safeguarding the rights and well-being of participants and ensuring the integrity of data collection. This included obtaining informed consent from participants, maintaining anonymity and confidentiality throughout the survey process. Participants were assured that data security measures were in place to protect their privacy, and the survey design and implementation upheld principles of fairness and equity.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express her sincerest appreciation to those people who extended their helping hands, time, support and skills in making this study possible:

The researcher's adviser, Mr. Romnick E. Bontigao, for his guidance, invaluable insights and support throughout this study. His expertise and patience have been instrumental in shaping this study;

The researcher's dearest statistician, Dr. Melchor A. Villapando, for sharing his skills and expertise to validate the survey instrument to ensure its reliability and validity for data gathering;

The researcher would like also to extend her deepest gratitude and recognition to the panelists, Dr. Diosmar Fernandez and Dr. Ma. Lorena Tagala, and to the Dean of Graduate Studies, Mr. Alfredo Perez Jr., for the constructive criticisms and valuable suggestions throughout the evaluation and presentation, which made this research more credible;

Ms. Ushas Richel R. Rino, for her time and skills to improve the clarity and coherence of this study. Her keen eye for grammar and her invaluable contributions to refining the language and structure of my writing was very significant and valuable to this study;

The president of the Our Lady of Fatima University, campus admins, heads, instructors and employees, for giving their full support on this study. Without their permission and cooperation, this research would not be possible. She is deeply grateful for their time, cooperation, and invaluable contributions, which have enriched the depth and breadth of this study;

The researcher's, Joner Fundales, for his patience and sacrifices that have been the cornerstone of this success. She owes him immense gratitude for believing, cheering, and providing a nurturing environment that enabled her to pursue her academic goals and to finish this study;

The researcher's loved ones, her beloved parents, Ricardo Fulgar and Vida Luz Fulgar, and her brothers and sisters Esmeraldo, Kevin, Ricardo Jr., Crystal and Kathleen Fulgar for their unconditional love, support, and understanding which truly inspired her throughout this academic journey and to strive harder to finish this research study;

Above all, the researcher would like to offer her humble gratitude to Almighty God for guiding her, for providing her with the knowledge, strength, inspiration, wisdom and clarity of purpose, which have sustained the researcher every step of the way.

REFERENCES

- Abebe, S. (2019). Client satisfaction with existing labor and delivery care and associated factors among mothers who gave birth in university of Gondar teaching hospital; Northwest Ethiopia: Institution based cross-sectional study. *Plos One Journals*.
<https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0210693>
- Aktar, S. (2021). The Impacts of Service Quality on Client Satisfaction: An Empirical Study on Private Commercial Banks in Bangladesh. *Canadian Journal of*

- Business and Information Studies*. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Mst-Aktar-5/publication/354477668_The_Impacts_of_Service_Quality_on_Client_Satisfacti on_An_Empirical_Study_on_Private_Commercial_Banks_in_Bangladesh/links/613a5a932712181801ce40ba/The-Impacts-of-Service-Quality-on-Clie
- Almaser, A. (2020). The impact of employee satisfaction on customer satisfaction: Theoretical and empirical underpinning. *Growing Science*. <http://m.growingscience.com/beta/msl/4068-the-impact-of-employee-satisfaction-%20on-customer-satisfaction-theoretical-and-empirical-underpinning.html>
- Anwar, A. (2021). Work Engagement: How Does Employee Work Engagement influence Employee Satisfaction? *SSRN Journals*. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3863600
- Clements, J. (2023, March 28). The Future of Record Management System. *Managed Outsource Solutions*. <https://www.managedoutsource.com/blog/the-future-of-record-management-system/>
- Edmans, A. (2023, August). Employee Satisfaction, Labor Market Flexibility, and Stock Returns Around the World. *Pubsonline*. <https://pubsonline.informs.org/doi/abs/10.1287/mnsc.2023.4889>
- Guerrini, M., & Possemato, T. (2019). From record management to data management: RDA and new application models BIBFRAME, RIMMF, and OliSuite/WeCat. *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly*, 54(3), 179–199. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2016.1144667>
- Haddad, A., Habaebi, M. H., Islam, M. R., Hasbullah, N. F., & Zabidi, S. A. (2022). Systematic Review on AI-Blockchain Based E-Healthcare Records Management Systems. *IEEE Access*, 10, 94583–94615. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2022.3201878>
- Ishtiaq, M. (2019). Book Review Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. *English Language Teaching*, 12(5), 40. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v12n5p40>
- Lee, S. W., Sung, H. J., & Jeon, H. M. (2019). Determinants of Continuous Intention on Food Delivery Apps: Extending UTAUT2 with Information Quality. *Sustainability*, 11(11), 3141. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11113141>
- Malak, H. A. (2022). What is Records Management Implementation Plan? November 6. *THE ECM Consultant*. <https://theecmconsultant.com/records-management-implementation-plan/>
- Mukne. (2020). Land Record Management using Hyperledger Fabric and IPFS. *IEEE Explore*. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8944471>
- Ofori, K. (2022). Do business records management affect business growth? *Plos One Journals*. <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0264135>
- Pandey. (2021). Exploring Blockchain and Smart Contract Technology for Reliable and Secure Land Registration and Record Management. *Springer Link*. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11277-021-08833-1>
- Pennix, G. (2020). *Records Management Handbook*. Google Books. <https://books.google.com.ph/books?hl=en&lr=&id=SIFBDgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=>

PT15&dq=record+management&ots=i9auaAU12o&sig=hz5lDmfhXe_QdsOOfWq
sN57DFDc&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=record%20management&f=false

Touray, R. (2021, December). A Review of Records Management in Organisations.
Scientific Research: An Academic Publisher.

<https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation.aspx?paperid=113666>

Yeo, K. (2022). A Conceptual Framework to Ensure Privacy in Patient Record
Management System. IEEE Explore.

<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9646903>